

Reflections on Incorporating Alternative Dispute Resolution into Environmental Dispute Resolution in Tanzania: Lessons from South Africa

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Abstract:

This article examines the legal framework for Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) and the incorporation of its diverse mechanisms into the resolution of environmental disputes in Tanzania. It also undertakes a brief analysis of the framework in South Africa which recognized ADR models in the resolution of environmental disputes. The South African regime can serve as a policy reference point for Tanzania. South Africa's National Environmental Management Act (NEMA) explicitly authorizes the use of ADR in the resolution of environmental disputes. Furthermore, the South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries and Environment (DFFE) promotes ADR as a medium for the peaceful and efficient resolution of environmental conflicts. However, this is a sharp contrast to the legal regime in Tanzania, where the flexibility of ADR has not been convincingly utilized both by regulatory and institutional processes, as well as parties to environmental disputes. Among other things, the article examines the Environmental Management Act of Tanzania and the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC) of Tanzania with a view to see how the resolution of environmental disputes can be strengthened through the use of ADR.

Keywords: Alternative Dispute Resolution, Environmental Dispute, Mediation, Arbitration, Tanzania, South Africa.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental disputes generally refer to conflicts arising from the use and protection of natural resources or the impact of human activities on the environment. These disputes can take various forms, including disagreements over land use, pollution, and resource allocation.¹ An “environmental dispute” can be viewed as any existing or anticipated difference or disagreement or dispute regarding the protection of the environment or the use of natural resources.² Environmental disputes arise from conflicting interests regarding land use, resource allocation, and the protection of ecological systems. These disputes can manifest in various forms, each presenting unique challenges and necessitating specific resolutions³. One prevalent type includes disputes over land use, particularly regarding activities such as industrial development, mining, and agriculture. These conflicts often pit economic development against ecological preservation, leading to substantial legal ramifications. Another significant category involves resource management disputes, commonly seen in water rights and air quality cases. Here, the contention typically revolves around the over-extraction of resources or pollution that affects public health and the environment.⁴

Moreover, there are disputes concerning biodiversity and habitat protection. These cases often arise when development projects threaten endangered species or critical habitats. These conflicts highlight the need for a balanced approach to environmental stewardship and sustainable development⁵. Lastly, a growing number of disputes entail transboundary issues, where environmental damage or resource exploitation affects multiple jurisdictions, complicating arbitration processes and legal governance. Understanding these types of environmental disputes is crucial as ADR mechanisms increasingly plays a role in their resolution.

1. CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR)

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) refers to a set of practices and techniques designed to resolve legal disputes outside formal court processes. It encompasses methods such as mediation, arbitration, conciliation, negotiation, and hybrid mechanisms through which a neutral party facilitates dispute settlement without resorting to traditional litigation.

¹Editorial (2023), Understanding environmental disputes and arbitration processes. LawHub. Retrieved from <https://lawhub.blog/environmental-disputes-and-arbitration>. Accessed on 1 August 2025.

² Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment. (n.d.). Environment sector conflict and dispute resolution. Republic of South Africa Institutional Report.

³ Editorial. (2023). Understanding environmental disputes and arbitration processes. LawHub. Retrieved from <https://lawhub.blog/environmental-disputes-and-arbitration>. Accessed on 2 September 2025.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid

ADR is increasingly recognized in both domestic and international legal systems for its flexibility, efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and ability to preserve relationships compared to adversarial court proceedings.⁶ To date, "alternative dispute resolution" or "appropriate dispute resolution" (ADR) is increasingly becoming a common practice in many judicial processes around the world. This is because of its many benefits as compared to other judicial mechanisms of dispute resolution.⁷

2.2 Conciliation

Conciliation, a dispute settlement mode that involves an independent "conciliator" who facilitates communication or discussions between two disputing parties to achieve an amicable settlement or resolution of a dispute between them.⁸ The conciliator does not take part in the process or settlement discussions but acts as a broker, bringing people together.⁹

2.3 Negotiation

Negotiation is the most direct form of ADR, involving the parties themselves, sometimes with the assistance of advisors, working collaboratively to resolve their dispute without third-party involvement. It is typically used when the parties remain on amicable terms and can engage constructively, making it a cost-effective and flexible method of settlement.¹⁰

2.4 Mediation

Mediation is a voluntary and confidential process in which a neutral third party (the mediator) assists disputing parties to identify issues, explore possible solutions, and reach a mutually acceptable agreement. The mediator does not decide the case but facilitates dialogue, helping parties to focus on their underlying interests and develop creative solutions. Mediation is valued for being less adversarial, relationship-preserving, and adaptable to a wide range of disputes.¹¹

⁶ Mnookin, R. H. (1998). *Alternative Dispute Resolution* (Discussion Paper No. 232). Harvard Law School, John M. Olin Centre for Law, Economics and Business. NELLCO Legal Scholarship Repository. P.2

⁷ Mashamba, J. C. (2020). *Guiding notes on mediation*. Tanganyika Law Society. P.7

⁸ Mashamba, J. C. (2020). *Ibid*. P.6

⁹ Mswahela, D. B. (2021). *Principles of Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania Manual*. Mzumbe University, Tanzania, P.32.

¹⁰ Mswahela, D. B. (2021). *Op cit* P.35.

¹¹ Mswahela, D. B. (2021). *Op Cit* P.50.

2.5 Arbitration

Arbitration is a more formal ADR process in which disputing parties agree to submit their case to one or more neutral arbitrators who have the authority to make a binding decision after hearing evidence and arguments. Unlike mediation or conciliation, arbitration results in an enforceable award, often recognized both domestically and internationally. It is particularly suited to complex commercial, contractual, and cross-border disputes where finality and neutrality are essential.¹² This means that parties submit a dispute to the decision of a neutral person or persons appointed by mutual consent or in accordance with the provisions of this Act.¹³

3. THE CURRENT FRAMEWORK FOR RESOLVING ENVIRONMENTAL DISPUTES

The Environmental Management Act as per section 3 defines environment as including the physical factors of the surroundings of human beings, including air, land, water, climate, sound, light, odour, taste, micro-organism, the biological factors of animals and plants, cultural resources and the social and economic factors of aesthetics and includes both the natural and the built environment and the way they interact.¹⁴ Environmental disputes have become increasingly common in Tanzania due to growing pressures on natural resources, pollution, and land-use conflicts. While the Environmental Management Act (EMA) serves as the principal legal framework for environmental protection and management in Tanzania, it establishes a broad basis for environmental governance.¹⁵ Specifically, it provides for environmental planning¹⁶ pollution control measures,¹⁷ natural resource management, and the overarching framework for environmental protection in the country. The EMA has established institutions mandated to handle environmental disputes, including the National Environment Management

¹² Mashamba, J. C. (2020). Guiding notes on mediation. Tanganyika Law Society.P.6.

¹³ Mswahela, D. B. (2021). Principles of Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania Manual. Mzumbe University, Tanzania, P.68

¹⁴ Section 3 of CAP 191, R.E. 2023. Defines environment” includes the physical factors of the surroundings of human beings including air, land, water, climate, sound, light, odour, taste, micro-organism, the biological factors of animals and plants, cultural resources and the social economic factor of aesthetics and includes both the natural and the built environment and the way they interact;

¹⁵ Ibid. Cap 191 R.E 2023.

¹⁶ Ibid, Section 86. That; The Council shall, upon examination of a project brief, require the proponent of a project or undertaking to carry out an Environmental Impact Assessment study and prepare an Environmental Impact Statement.

¹⁷ Ibid, Section 106. That, it shall be an offence for a person to pollute or permit any other person to pollute the environment in violation of any standards prescribed under this Act or any other written law regulating a segment of the environment.

Council under Section 16¹⁸ of the EMA; the Minister under Section 18(3)¹⁹ of EMA, and the Environmental Appeals Tribunal under Section 204²⁰ of the same Act.

3.1 Compliance and enforcement under EMA

Part XVI, sections 182-204 of the Environmental Management Act set out Tanzania's framework for enforcing compliance and resolving environmental disputes. It empowers environmental inspectors to investigate, issue orders, and take enforcement actions to prevent or remedy harm. Offenders may face penalties including heavy fines, imprisonment, restoration obligations, or cancellation of licences, while some cases can be settled through compounding of offences by the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC). Courts are given powers to order confiscation, community work, and environmental restoration. Importantly, Section 202 grants individuals, organizations, and communities the right to sue in their own interest, in the public interest, or on behalf of the environment itself, ensuring wide access to justice. Overall, the resolution process is largely litigation and enforcement-driven, with limited space for ADR mechanisms.

4. THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION IN TANZANIA

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Tanzania is understood as a set of mechanisms that allow parties to resolve disputes outside the traditional courtroom system. These mechanisms include negotiation, mediation, conciliation, and arbitration, each of which emphasizes flexibility, party autonomy and consensus rather than adversarial litigation. Historically, ADR in Tanzania draws from customary dispute resolution systems, where disputes were handled by elders or clan leaders with the primary goal of restoring harmony and preserving community relationships. These traditional practices continue to influence modern statutory laws, especially in land and environmental matters. These traditional practices continue to influence modern statutory laws, especially in land and environmental matters. Modern Tanzanian law formally recognizes ADR as a complement to litigation. The Civil Procedure Code incorporates mediation into the court process under Order VIII, Rule 24 and 25.²¹ Courts are required to encourage parties to

¹⁸ Section 16 states that; There shall be a Council to be known as the National Environment Management Council, also to be known by acronym "NEMC". Notwithstanding the provisions of this section, the Attorney General shall have the right to intervene in any suit or matter instituted by, or against the Council.

¹⁹ Section 18(3) provides that, A person who is aggrieved by the decision of the Council under this section may appeal to the Minister.

²⁰ There shall be established the Environmental Appeals Tribunal which shall consist of- (a) a Chairman who shall be appointed by the President from amongst the persons qualified to be appointed a judge.

²¹ CAP 33 R.E. 2023. States that, Subject to the provisions of any written law, the court shall refer every civil action for negotiation, conciliation, mediation, arbitration or similar alternative procedure, before proceeding for trial.

settle disputes amicably before proceeding to trial. This provision demonstrates the government's policy of reducing case backlogs and promoting peaceful settlements.²²

Judicial practice has also affirmed the legitimacy of ADR in Tanzania. In *National Insurance Corporation v Shengena Ltd*,²³ the Court of Appeal reiterated the principle of minimal judicial intervention in arbitral matters, confirming arbitration as a valid and enforceable mechanism of dispute settlement. This decision demonstrates that, Tanzanian courts support the development of ADR as part of the justice system; a position that can be extended to environmental disputes if appropriate statutory reforms are enacted.

Environmental disputes arise from conflicts over the use, management, and protection of natural resources and ecosystems such as forests, rivers, minerals, wildlife, or land, or situations in which environmental concerns are at stake. These disputes often stem from competing interests among different stakeholders, including governments, industries, communities, and environmental organizations, the state, and private actors, touching on land, forestry, mining, wildlife conservation, water use, and industrial pollution.²⁴ For example, a dispute may emerge when a government permits industrial activities to pollute, affecting the health and well-being of nearby communities.²⁵

Conflicts can also arise over land use, such as disagreements between developers seeking to build infrastructure and conservationists advocating for the preservation of ecologically sensitive areas. Additionally, issues like water rights, deforestation, and climate change policies can spark disputes as diverse parties with varying interests contend over the sustainable use of resources. The complexity of these disputes is heightened by differing perspectives on environmental impacts, economic priorities, and the overall balance between development and conservation. Unlike ordinary civil disputes, environmental disputes have a public interest dimension, since they affect not only the immediate parties but also future generations and ecological sustainability.

Common types of environmental disputes in Tanzania include conflicts between mining companies and local communities over land compensation, disputes between pastoralists and farmers over grazing and farming land, and disputes involving conservation

²² Kalabamu, F. T. (2021). Land conflicts and alternative dispute resolution in Sub-Saharan Africa: The case of Botswana. In S. Z. Zever (Ed.), *Land issues for urban governance in Sub-Saharan Africa* (pp. 171–187). Oxford University Press.

²³ (Civil Appeal No. 20 of 2007, CAT, unreported).

²⁴ Saruni, K., Urassa, J., & Kajembe, G. (2018). *Population pressure, environmental degradation, and land conflicts in Tanzania*. Mkuki na Nyota Publishers.

²⁵ Opperman, C (2024). *Green-Mediation Strategies for Resolving Environmental Conflicts*.P.9.

authorities such as the Tanzania National Parks Authority (TANAPA) or the Ngorongoro Conservation Area Authority (NCAA), where human settlements overlap with protected areas.²⁶ For example, conflicts have arisen in areas where communities are displaced or restricted from accessing natural resources due to conservation or investment projects. Such disputes highlight the tension between developmental interests, environmental protection, and community rights, a balance that ADR mechanisms are well-suited to address by promoting dialogue and compromise.

4.1 The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania

The Constitution of Tanzania provides the fundamental legal foundation for environmental protection, sustainable resource use, and the rights and duties of citizens, which in turn underpin the legal framework for resolving environmental disputes. The essence of Article 107A (d) of the Tanzanian Constitution is to promote and enhance dispute resolution among persons involved in disputes.²⁷ The Constitution of Tanzania embeds environmental protection within fundamental rights and duties. Article 14 guarantees the right to life, which is interpreted to include a clean and healthy environment, making environmental disputes a public interest issue.²⁸ Article 27(1) obliges every citizen to safeguard natural resources,²⁹ while Article 9(c) directs the government to ensure their sustainable use for present and future generations.³⁰

4.2 Environmental Management Act

The Environmental Management Act is Tanzania's principal legislation on environmental governance.³¹ Unlike other statutes, the Act does not explicitly provide for Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms such as mediation, arbitration, or conciliation in resolving environmental disputes. Instead, it emphasizes regulatory compliance, enforcement measures, and institutional responsibilities. Section 4 establishes the right of every person to a clean and healthy environment,³² while section 18 allows individuals to take legal action in the public interest, which may be pursued through formal or

²⁶ Ampeire, A. (2017). *Alternative dispute resolution: Mediation, conciliation, arbitration*. Fountain Publishers.

²⁷ The constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, Cap 2 of 1977, provides that, to promote and enhance dispute resolution among persons involved in the disputes; and to dispense justice without being tied up with technicalities provisions which may obstruct dispensation of justice.

²⁸ Ibid, Article 14; Every person has the right to live and to the protection of his life by the society in accordance with the law.

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ Article 27(1) states that; Every person has the duty to protect the natural resources of the United Republic, the property of the state authority, all property collectively owned by the people, and also to respect another person's property.

³¹ Cap 191 R.E. 2023.

³² Section 4 provides that, A person living in Tanzania shall have a right to clean, safe and healthy environment

informal means.³³ The Environmental Management Act establishes the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC), which plays a quasi-judicial role in receiving complaints, conducting investigations, and reviewing as per section 16³⁴ establishes the institution, section 17³⁵ provides for its purpose and section 18 provides for the function of this Institution of the Environmental Management Act.

4.3 Arbitration Act

The Arbitration Act establishes a comprehensive framework for arbitration, defining procedures for appointing arbitrators, enforcing awards, and recognizing international arbitral decisions.³⁶ Although the Act applies broadly to civil and commercial disputes, its provisions extend to environmental matters where arbitration agreements exist, particularly in sectors such as mining, oil, gas and infrastructure projects. In section 5(1)(a)(b) and (c), the Arbitration Act articulates the following objectives: to obtain the fair resolution of disputes by an impartial arbitral tribunal without undue delay or incurring of unreasonable expense; to promote consistency between domestic and international arbitration; the parties shall be free to agree how their disputes are resolved, subject only to such safeguards as are necessary in the public interest; and in matters governed by this Act, the court shall not intervene except as provided by this Act.³⁷

4.4 Legal Aid Act

Section 20 (2) (d) of the Legal Aid Act allows paralegals to provide legal aid services, especially to indigent persons who apply for assistance.³⁸ Their duties include educating communities on legal issues, helping clients obtain legal documents, guiding them to the proper forum for justice, and, importantly, advising conflicting parties to pursue amicable settlement or referring them to dispute resolution institutions. This highlights the Act's role in promoting ADR by encouraging early settlement of disputes and widening access to justice for marginalized groups. The Legal and Human Rights Centre (LHRC) has a legal aid center in Kinondoni where it receives few environmental disputes, about 5 to 6

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Cap 191, R.E 2023. Supra.

³⁵ Ibid. Cap 191, R.E 2023. Supra.

³⁶ Cap 15 R.E. 2023

³⁷ Ibid, Section 5 states that; The provisions of this Act are founded on the following principles, and shall be construed accordingly: (a) the object of arbitration is- (i) to obtain the fair resolution of disputes by an impartial arbitral tribunal without undue delay or incurring of unreasonable expense; and (ii) to promote consistency between domestic and international arbitration; (b) the parties shall be free to agree how their disputes are resolved, subject only to such safeguards as are necessary in the public interest.

³⁸ Legal Aid Act, Cap 21, R.E 2023. See Section 20(2)(d) states that, without prejudice to the generality of subsection (1), a paralegal shall have the following duties: (d) advising the conflicting parties to seek amicable settlement or referring them to dispute settlement institutions.

per year. Most of the disputes are complaints on noise pollution, which are addressed by mediation.³⁹

4.5 Village Land Act

Section 60(1)(2) of the Village Land Act empowers village councils to mediate environmental disputes before they are reported to higher authorities.⁴⁰ Section 67(1) of the Act provides for appeal procedures, allowing parties dissatisfied with the village council's mediated settlement to escalate the matter to the district land and housing tribunal. Instance of the application of the Village Land Act in Tanzania include disputes between farmers and pastoralists in Morogoro and Kilosa regions, where village councils mediate agreements on sharing land, access to water, and grazing schedules. Similarly, disputes over forest resources or community land used for conservation or irrigation projects have been successfully resolved through village-level mediation, often including environmental restoration or compensation.

4.6 Land Disputes Courts Act

The Land Disputes Courts Act provides a hierarchical framework for resolving land and related environmental disputes, emphasizing mediation at all levels.⁴¹ Ward tribunals attempt conciliation before cases reach district tribunals, which can also facilitate settlements after filing as per section 8(1) and section 14(1). This community-based ADR approach promotes negotiated, socially and environmentally sustainable solutions, reducing conflict and ensuring compliance with environmental standards, as seen in regions Ifakara.⁴²

The Village Land Act, and the Land Dispute Court Act provisions illustrate that while land-related legislations expressly promote ADR as a mechanism of dispute settlement, the Environmental Management Act remains silent on the matter, thereby weakening the framework for the peaceful resolution of environmental conflicts on other natural resources.

³⁹ TANZANIA HUMAN RIGHTS REPORT 2024, Mainland Tanzania - Legal and Human Rights Centre (LHRC). Available at <https://humanrights.or.tz/en/post/resources-center/thrr2024report>. Accessed on 1 August 2025.

⁴⁰ Village Land Act, Cap 114 R.E. 2023

⁴¹ Cap 216 R.E 2023

⁴² Kamoleka, T. (2024). Evaluating alternative dispute resolution in resolving land conflicts in Ifakara, Tanzania.

5. THE CASE FOR INSTITUTIONALIZING ADR IN ENVIRONMENTAL DISPUTES

The institutionalization of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) within environmental governance has emerged as a compelling strategy to address the unique challenges posed by environmental conflicts. Unlike ordinary civil disputes, environmental matters often involve multiple stakeholders, complex technical issues, and questions of public interest that transcend private rights. These features make litigation costly, adversarial, and often inadequate in producing holistic remedies. Institutionalizing ADR by embedding mediation, conciliation, arbitration, and hybrid processes within the statutory and institutional framework offers an opportunity to create a structured, reliable, and accessible pathway for resolving such disputes. This section explores the merits of institutionalizing ADR in environmental governance, highlights its potential drawbacks, and proposes safeguards to ensure ADR contributes effectively to environmental justice.

For instance, international jurisprudence has illustrated ADR's suitability for technically complex and public-interest disputes. In *Mitsubishi Motors Corp v Soler Chrysler-Plymouth*,⁴³ the United States Supreme Court upheld the arbitration of complex antitrust claims, recognizing arbitration as capable of addressing specialized statutory matters. By analogy, environmental disputes, which often require technical expertise and swift remedies, are equally well suited to ADR processes.

Moreover, ADR processes are generally faster and less expensive than court litigation. Environmental disputes often require urgent intervention to prevent irreversible harm, such as continued pollution or destruction of ecosystems. ADR's expedited timelines allow remedies to be designed and implemented more quickly, thereby mitigating harm while avoiding the delays and costs associated with prolonged litigation.⁴⁴ Unlike courts, which are constrained by formal remedies, ADR mechanisms allow parties to design creative, site-specific solutions. For example, a mediated settlement might include community reforestation programs, compensation schemes, or environmental monitoring arrangements, remedies not typically available through judicial orders. This adaptability is particularly important in environmental disputes, which frequently require scientific and technical input.⁴⁵ Environmental conflicts often involve ongoing relationships between communities, investors, and government agencies. Mediation and conciliation encourage dialogue, cooperation, and joint problem-solving, which can

⁴³ Inc 473 U.S. 614 (1985).

⁴⁴ Mnookin, R.H., Alternative Dispute Resolution (Harvard Law School Discussion Paper No. 232, 1998)

⁴⁵ Opperman, C., Green-Mediation Strategies for Resolving Environmental Conflicts (2024).

preserve relationships and foster long-term collaboration. By contrast, litigation tends to polarize parties and entrench hostility.⁴⁶

Courts in Tanzania, as in many developing jurisdictions, face significant case backlogs. By institutionalizing ADR, a portion of environmental disputes can be resolved outside courtrooms, freeing judicial resources for cases that require authoritative adjudication. Moreover, where ADR outcomes are formally recognized, they can be converted into consent orders or enforceable agreements, reducing enforcement burdens on the courts.⁴⁷

However, a key strength of ADR which is confidentiality may become a weakness in environmental disputes, which often implicate public goods such as air, water, and biodiversity. Settlements negotiated in private may lack sufficient transparency or public input, undermine democratic oversight and potentially permit environmentally harmful compromises.⁴⁸ Environmental disputes frequently pit local communities against powerful corporations or state entities. Without robust safeguards, ADR processes may replicate or exacerbate these power asymmetries. Communities may lack legal or technical expertise, resulting in agreements that fail to reflect their true interests or adequately protect the environment.⁴⁹ While ADR agreements can be creative, they risk being ineffective if not properly enforced. Voluntary compliance is not always reliable, especially where economic incentives favour continued environmental harm. Without statutory provisions to register and enforce ADR outcomes, parties may renege on their commitments, undermining trust in the system.⁵⁰

5.1 Addressing the challenges

To institutionalize ADR effectively, several safeguards and reforms are required. Environmental legislation, such as the Environmental Management Act, should explicitly recognize ADR as a legitimate mechanism for dispute resolution, while defining its scope. For instance, ADR could be mandated for community-level disputes and regulatory compliance issues, while courts retain jurisdiction over constitutional and precedent-setting matters.⁵¹ Institutionalization requires the establishment of accredited panels of

⁴⁶ Ampeire, A., *Alternative Dispute Resolution: Mediation, Conciliation, Arbitration* (Fountain Publishers, 2017).

⁴⁷ Mashamba, J.C., *Guiding Notes on Mediation* (Tanganyika Law Society, 2020).

⁴⁸ Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (South Africa), *Environment Sector Conflict and Dispute Resolution* (n.d.).

⁴⁹ Editorial, 'Understanding Environmental Disputes and Arbitration Processes' LawHub (2023) <https://lawhub.blog/environmental-disputes-and-arbitration>. Accessed on 2 September 2025.

⁵⁰ Saruni, K., Urassa, J. & Kajembe, G., *Population Pressure, Environmental Degradation, and Land Conflicts in Tanzania* (Mkuki na Nyota, 2018).

⁵¹ Somi, E., 'Social, Economic and Environmental Justice: Institutional Gaps in Tanzania's Environmental Regulations' (2022) *South African Journal of Social and Economic Policy* 83.

environmental mediators and arbitrators. These neutrals must combine dispute resolution skills with technical expertise in ecology, environmental science, and social impact assessment. Ongoing training and monitoring should be compulsory to maintain standards.

To counteract power imbalances, parties, particularly communities, must have access to independent legal and technical advice, potentially funded by legal aid or public-interest organizations. Screening processes should be implemented to ensure ADR is not pursued where power disparities cannot be adequately managed. ADR agreements should be registrable with courts or environmental authorities to give them the force of law. Statutory provisions could empower the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC) or specialized tribunals to supervise compliance and impose sanctions for breach. For disputes with significant public interest implications, settlements should not be entirely confidential. Legislation could require public notice of ADR processes, opportunities for third-party submissions, and publication of non-confidential terms of settlement. This would balance confidentiality with accountability.

6. LESSONS FROM SOUTH AFRICA

South Africa's experience provides valuable lessons in how to institutionalize ADR for environmental protection. Under the National Environmental Management Act (NEMA) (Act 107 of 1998), Chapter 4 explicitly authorizes the use of ADR mechanisms such as mediation, facilitation, and arbitration in environmental disputes and obliges decision-makers to consider criteria including speedy and cheap resolution, accessibility for indigent persons, and participation of affected persons.⁵² Despite these strong legal provisions, empirical studies show a persistent gap between theory and practice: ADR remains underutilized in environmental cases, due to a lack of awareness, insufficient institutional capacity, both in trained neutrals and funding, and weak enforcement or follow-up of mediated agreements.⁵³

South Africa has therefore demonstrated that legal authorization, while necessary, is not sufficient. Success depends on building a well-resourced institutional infrastructure, ensuring procedural safeguards for weaker parties, providing public information and monitoring of outcomes, and ensuring that ADR decisions have pathways to

⁵² Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment. (n.d.). Environment sector conflict and dispute resolution. Republic of South Africa. Retrieved from <https://www.dffe.gov.za/environment-sector-conflict-and-dispute-resolution>. Accessed on 3 September 2025.

⁵³ Ngombane, S. (2018). Alternative dispute resolution: A mechanism for resolving environmental disputes in South Africa (Master's thesis, University of the Free State). University of the Free State Institutional Repository. <https://scholar.ufs.ac.za/items/oode7180-ea99-4014-b373-c146b366cb56>. Accessed on 4 September 2025.

enforceability.⁵⁴ In *Fuel Retailers Association of Southern Africa v Director-General Environmental Management, Mpumalanga*,⁵⁵ the Constitutional Court emphasized the importance of inclusive and participatory processes in environmental decision-making. While the case did not directly involve ADR, its reasoning supports the idea that mediation and facilitation can strengthen public involvement in environmental governance. This complements the statutory framework under the National Environmental Management Act (NEMA), which explicitly authorizes ADR processes for environmental disputes.

7. CONCLUSION

ADR has clear advantages for environmental disputes: flexibility, technical tailoring, cost and time savings, and potential for negotiated cooperative outcomes. South Africa's statutory recognition of ADR in NEMA shows a policy pathway Tanzania can emulate. However, statutory recognition alone is insufficient. Effective ADR requires accredited, technically competent mediators, clear procedures for converting settlements into enforceable measures, transparency safeguards for public interest matters, and institutional investment. By adopting tailored legal reforms, accreditation standards, and capacity building informed by South African experience, Tanzania can strengthen its ADR systems and improve environmental dispute outcomes for communities, regulators, and private actors alike.

⁵⁴ Alder, J. (2014). The use of mediation to resolve environmental disputes in South Africa and Switzerland (Master's dissertation, University of Cape Town). CORE. <https://core.ac.uk/outputs/29053071>. Accessed on 1 September 2025.

⁵⁵ [2007] ZACC 13.